

In 1985-88 trials, grain yields were generally slightly higher at Befang. Plants were shorter and growth duration much longer at Babungo (see table), reflecting the cooler temperatures that adversely affected crop growth there. The highest yielding entries were ITA208 and IRAT109 at Befang and IRAT112 and IRAT109 at Babungo. Across sites, the highest yields were from IRAT109, ITA208, and IRAT112.

IRAT 109, a derivative of IRAT 13/IRAT10, has medium-long grain with white bran. IRAT112 from IRAT13/Dourado Precoce is similar to IRAT109 in agronomic trait, but has slender grain, which is more acceptable to consumers. ITA208, a derivative of 63-83/(Vijaya, Dourado Precoce, Jumai) has medium-long, bold grain with white bran. ROK16, a selection from the traditional varieties of Sierra Leone, has broad leaves, awned spikelets, and medium and bold grains.

M55 is an improved upland variety currently grown by a few farmers. It is a mutant of 63-83 and has medium and bold grains. ■

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Integrated germplasm improvement — deepwater

Three promising deepwater rice varieties for Sichuan

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About 200,000 ha of tanks, weirs, and lakes in Sichuan Province with water depths of 50-150 cm are the primary source of irrigation water for a large hectareage of irrigated ricelands. The introduction of deepwater rice cultivation could increase total production, and better meet the food needs of a rapidly growing population.

In 1988-89, we evaluated promising deepwater rice cultivars IR41336-6-2-1-1, B4406D-MR-2-7, and B5278-13D-

MR-6-3 selected from the International Rice Deep Water Observational Nursery (IRDWON). IR41336-6-2-1-1-1 was derived from RD19/Badal 116; B4406D-MR-2-7 from SML Tomerin/B2360-6-7-1//Tetep/B2474B-1-PN-2-3-2-2-5; and B5278-13D-MR-6-3 from Lagos/IR9129-457-2-2-1-2//FR13A/IR3351-38-3-1.

They appear to be adaptable to Sichuan circumstances and are being

recommended for demonstration trials in farmers' fields (see table). IR41336-6-2-1-1-1 has strong culms and dark green leaves, with medium slender, fine, white grain. B4406D-MR-2-7 and B5278-13D-MR-6-3 have medium bold grain. All three cultivars have very good submergence tolerance, kneeling ability, and plant type. They are moderately resistant to blast. ■

Agricultural characteristics of 3 promising deepwater rice cultivars in Luzhou, Sichuan, China (mean of 1988-1989).

Character	IR41336-6-2-1-1-1	B4406D-MR-2-7	B5278-13D-MR-6-3
Culm length (cm)	155.4	136.3	141.7
Growth duration (d)	175.0	184.0	174.0
Panicles/plant (no.)	6.8	6.2	5.5
Panicle length (cm)	30.6	26.8	32.4
Filled spikelets/panicle (no.)	178.3	138.6	161.2
1000-grain weight (g)	24.7	25.4	27.8
Grain yield (t/ha)	3.4	3.3	3.2

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soils

Exchangeable Al as a criterion of lime requirement for rice in acid sulfate soil

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A field study was conducted to determine whether exchangeable Al can serve as basis for lime requirement to maximize the yield of rice in an acid sulfate soil.

Effects of lime levels on yield and nutrient uptake of rice grown in acid sulfate soil. Nirdeshkali, West Bengal.

Lime rate (t CaCO ₃ /ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Nutrient uptake (mg/kg)				
		N	P	K	Fe	Al
No lime	1.7	21.0	6.7	47.1	10.2	8.1
3.6	2.0	22.2	7.4	49.8	9.8	7.5
5.5	2.3	25.0	7.7	50.2	8.9	7.5
7.3	2.3	28.2	9.5	60.2	7.8	6.6
9.1	4.0	51.6	20.0	70.4	4.5	4.2
11.0	3.8	48.4	19.9	70.7	4.5	5.0
12.8	3.7	47.8	19.3	70.9	5.0	4.9
14.6	3.3	48.6	18.4	72.9	4.6	5.1
16.4	3.0	46.5	11.3	73.4	5.1	5.2
18.2	2.8	35.9	7.1	59.4	5.3	5.3
LSD (0.01)	6.7	6.7	3.5	5.7	1.4	2.1